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DEVELOPING LISTENING SKILLS THROUGH SELECTED MOVIES: “LUCY, ALADDIN AND SPIDERMAN”

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ABSTRACT:

Aim of this study is to find the effect of Movies “Lucy, Aladdin and Spiderman” on the listening skills of students. Can movies, in general, affect listening skills off students? Can Movies Lucy, Aladdin and Spiderman improve listening skills of students? Are movies useful in the classroom to teach English? The present study tries to answer such questions. The experiment is done on students of experimental group and controlled group. The result shows that movies “Lucy, Aladdin and Spiderman” improve listening skills of students.

Keywords: Movie Scene, Experimental Group, Controlled Group, Pre-Test, And Post-Test.

Introduction

Movies have become an integral part of a student’s life. Students speak film’s dialogues more than a quotation from books. Movies are great sources to impart listening skills. A lot of problems are created daily because everybody wants to speak, people do not want to listen. Most people in this world are poor listeners. Because everybody wants to develop their speaking ability. Mostly they focus on writing, reading skills and speaking skills. Students have experienced mostly excise of speaking, reading comprehension and writing. One skill that is mostly neglected is listening skills and activities of listening. We have so many spoken classes in cities but we do not have listening classes. The focus needs to be turned toward listening from speaking. All good speakers in this world are better listeners. One of the reasons behind the poor speaking skills of students is poor listening. Developing listening skills through movies is not a new thing but it has not been done systematically, officially. Students watch English movies. They develop their listening skills. But effective development happens when they do exercise of it. Here it is an attempt to see how students can develop their listening skills through movies. Teacher’s involvement is a must.

Objective of the research

- ✦ To see that Movies “Lucy, Aladdin and Spiderman” improves listening skills of students
- ✦ To observe the effect of Movies on the acquisition of language.
- ✦ To add knowledge in the domain of ELT
- ✦ To inspire teachers to use movies in the classroom

Why Movies?

Movies play a major role in our speaking. It is listening that helps to speak. Movies impart much a lot of listening experiences. “When films are utilized as classroom texts, learning opportunities flourish and teachers have treasure troves of rich material from which to develop listening and all the other skills for every level of adult learners, and to create engaging projects in even the tightest of curricula.” (Holland 53) Movies improve pronunciation. Most of the time students make errors in pronunciation because they listen to incorrect pronunciation around them. Movies provide them with correct pronunciation from Native speakers.

Immersing in the authentic and vivid English context, through the subtitles and lively conversation, students can see the image and hear the pronunciation, use their background knowledge, and thus, fetch the main ideas of the movie. When students are engaged in the listening activity, subtitles can give them better emphasis or hint of what they should pay attention to. Clearly, using films is an effective way for students to improve their listening ability and get better insight in English culture. (Safranji 172)

Research Methodology

Students were divided into an experimental group and controlled group. Listening exercises from movies were given to the experimental group and General listening exercises were given to controlled groups. In this experiment pre-test is taken to know the level of students, After Pre-test, Experiment happens, after that Post-test is taken to know the development of listening skills in both group. The experiment was done on students of Engineering. Most of the students were found with A2 level in both groups. Students were evaluated with rubrics of CEFR level. Those students who were found with A2 level were selected for this experiment. Students of Controlled listen to conversations on general topics and Students of Experimental group

‘Lucy’ movie was selected for this experiment. Lucy (2014) is a science fiction movie. This listening comprehension is for B1 level. Following questions were asked from the Movie scene. Here professor explains how much mental capacity human and animal have and how much they are using. Here the speaker speaks slowly and very clearly.

(1) What can human being do with two neurons?

- (A) Human can see someone moving
- (B) Human can move.
- (C) They control other

(2) How much do most species use cerebral capacity?

(A) 3 to 5%

(B) 8 to 10%

(C) 1%

(3) Who uses brain capacity more than human being?

(A) Birds

(B) Dolphin

(C) Monkey

(4) What can human being do with 20% human capacity?

(A) Control their own body

(B) Control other's body

(C) Control animal's body

(5) What can human being do with 40% human capacity?

(A) Control their own body

(B) Control other

(C) Control animal

The Second movie was Aladdin. It is a 2019 American musical fantasy film produced by Walt Disney Pictures. Following listening comprehension was used.

(1) You should see these places I mean

There's a whole world outside _____

(2) Sometimes princess sometimes you just have to take _____

(3) What just happened is this _____

(4) Do you _____ me?

(5) I can make you rich, rich enough to impress _____

What would I have to do?

(6) There's _____

(7) Hey can you make me a _____?

(8) I'm in _____okay I say when it's done

(9) I thought a princess could go _____Not this princess.

The third movie is Spiderman (2002). No introduction is needed about this film, as it is so famous movies all over the world. Conversation between Peter (Spiderman) and his uncle is chosen here to impart listening skills. There are two exercises. Students are supposed to find out a character who speaks certain dialogues in A exercise in B exercise, students arrange the sequence of jumbled dialogues. (A) Find out who speaks dialogues.

Sr.	Dialogues	Characters
1	What do we have to talk about right now?	(Example) Peter
2	No I need the exercise	
3	I don't start that fight I told you that well	
4	Then stop pretending to be	
5	I'll take the train.	
6	I don't start that fight I told you	
7	Right I'll pick you up here	
8	Thanks for the ride	
9	Great power comes with great responsibility	

(B) Follow sequence and give right sequence no.

Sr.	Dialogues	Right sequence no
1	We can talk now if you let me	
2	Hey go to the downtown library see you later yeah	
3	If he's too embarrassed to tell me what it is maybe, I'm too embarrassed to ask	
4	What do we have to talk about right now?	
5	Wait Pete I'll uh I'll Drive you there buddy	
6	No you're not supposed to run away	

7	Thanks for the ride	
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Result

In above listening comprehension section, Students scored maximum marks. It concludes that students had A2 level but when they practised listening through movies. Students improved their listening skills. It suggest that students are interested listening if it is done by movies. It also indicates that students do not get bored. Students are excited to experience something new. pre-test and post-test of both groups Experimental and Controlled group were compared and analysed. Following charts simplify to understand result

Figure-1

Above the chart of Experimental group shows clearly that students of Experimental group scored more marks in Post-test than Pre-test. Above the chart of Controlled group also indicates that students scored more marks in Post-test than Pre-test but When various ion of post-test of Both groups experimental and controlled groups is compared and analysed. It

clearly shows that result of Experimental group is much high compared to the controlled group.

Conclusion

This study concludes that Movies “Lucy, Aladdin and Spiderman” are able to develop listening skills. It is also found that Movies are great sources to improve the listening skills of learners. The study inspires teachers to use movies in the classroom to develop not just listening skills but also all four skills of Language. The output of this research adds fruitful contribution to the domain of ELT.

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